

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ANTIBIOTIC REGIMENS FOR LUNG ABSCESS TREATMENT

Choudhary A.H

Student of faculty of general medicine, Samarkand state medical university

Department of internal medicine and cardiology

Scientific advisor - assistant professor **Abdullayeva Z.A.**

Introduction. Lung abscess is a common clinical problem in developing countries, the mortality rate of lung abscess is 8.7%. Comparative study of the antibiotic regimens aim to determine appropriate and most effective treatment approach.

Research objective. To determine the safe treatment approach for this lung infection and identifying the most effective antibiotics, optimizing treatment duration. optimizing treatment duration and informing clinical guidelines, as it is potentially a life threatening condition. A descriptive statistical analysis also represented as absolute values and percentages was also done for the better regimen by comparing top research articles in order get a better clarity on regimen of lung abscess.

Materials and methods. a cohort study was performed in 3 patients groups to compare outcomes in patients receiving different antibiotics regimens over time. Group 1 had 15 patients (7 men and 8 women) they were administered with combination of ampicillin/sulbactam, group 2 had 14 patients (6 women and 8 men) they were administered with moxifloxacin had 12 patients (7 men and 5 women) were administered with clindamycin.

Research Results. In group 1 patients out of 15 patients 2 patients (13%) were allergic to ampicillin rest 13 patients responded very well to the therapy with very mild side effects, 11 patients (73%) complained about Nausea. The mean duration of therapy was 26.5 days and the clinical response was 75.5% and 68% 10-14 days after therapy. In group 2 patients mean duration of the therapy with moxifloxacin lasted for 40 days. The overall clinical response was 72% Moxifloxacin was also considered effective and well tolerated with 3 (21%) patients shown no side effects and 2 (14%) patients complained about diarrhea and nausea, 6 (42%) complained only about Nausea. Group 3 patients administered with clindamycin (600 mg IV). Mean duration of the therapy was 24.5 days and the clinical response was 68.5% at the end of therapy and 64.5% 7-14 days after the therapy.

Conclusion. the duration for the therapy with moxifloxacin was the longer (40 days) as compared with as that of ampicillin/sulbactam (26.5 days) and clindamycin (24.5 days). ampicillin and sulbactam having great overall clinical response of 75.5%. Ampicillin/sulbactam showed superior outcomes in terms of mean duration, reduced complication. resolution rates.